

International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction

A novel hybrid deep learning model for predicting spread of wildfire

--Manuscript Draft--

Manuscript Number:	
Article Type:	Research Paper
Keywords:	Fire spread; Deep learning; Wildfire; Forest fire; Long short term memory; Convolutional neural networks
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A novel hybrid deep learning model for predicting spread of wildfire

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Abstract

The environment has suffered billions of dollars in environmental damage due to destructive wildfires during the last twenty years. Wildfires are expected to become more dangerous in the near future as climate change increases their occurrence probability. It is vital to have a model which can predict wildfire growth over a variety of geographies, climates, and fuel types. Learning-based models often derive training data from running physical models. In this study, a hybrid deep learning model was developed based on real fire data and meteorological factors to predict wildfire spreading. We implemented a fully connected convolutional neural network long short term memory (FC-CNN-LSTM) model to predict the forest fire spread in the coming days by using an appropriate cost function. The FC-CNN-LSTM model was trained by using a set of related variables, including climate data, daily fire data, landcover data and topographic data. Our Proposed model compared to other deep learning models such as fully connected convolutional recurrent neural network (FCCRNN), neural network(NN), recurrent neural network(RNN), has higher accuracy, F1 score, precision and recall in predicting fire spread. According to our results deciduous shrubland can significantly influence a fire's spread. To determine the effects of a variable on fire spread, correlation analysis is used. Almost in most days of the fire, meteorological variables are inversely related to fire activity. Topographic factors often play a positive role in the spread of fire days and the intensity effect has increased with passing time.

Keywords

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1. Introduction and related works

During the last twenty years, destructive wildfires caused billions of dollars of damage to the environment. As climate change increases forest fires frequency, duration, and severity, are expected to be more destructive. The processes of geography and ecology such as wildfires, have a spatial dimension as dynamic systems [1]. In order for the environment to be sustainable, forests are a crucial part of its ecosystem [2]. Wildfires are one of the worst disasters that cause ecological damage and casualties to forests and people alike [3, 4]. During the forest fire in Victoria (Australia) in 1983, 392,000 hectares of land were burned and 75 people died [5]. 5.7 million hectares of land were affected by fires in India from 1985 to 1990, resulting in 17,852 reports [6]. 20 people died as a result of forest fires in Portugal in 2003, which destroyed 420,000 hectares [7]. The fires which ravaged Spain in 2006 caused an area of almost 150,000 hectares to burn [8]. Canada has an average of 8,000 fires per year and 2.5 million hectares of land is burned on average every year [9]. A wildfire spread across 11.2 million hectares of forests in September 2019 in the south-east of Australia that caused the deaths of countless animals, many of whom have been eliminated [10, 11]. To reduce the risks of human casualties and property damage caused by forest fires, forest management measures must be taken to promote preventative measures [12]. Also by detecting and predicting wildfires early, destructive repercussions from the fire can be greatly mitigated [13]. Nevertheless, the propagation and prediction of wildfires are complicated because the various factors and conditions interact with each other [14]. In order to properly predict wildfires' spread over numerous geographies, climates and fuel types, a fire spread model is vitally needed [15]. several approaches to predict wildland fire susceptibility and spread proposed [16, 17].

Researcher in various countries have been involved in forest fire research because of the global nature of the issue. There is a high degree of uncertainty involved in modeling dynamic processes on the Earth's surface because it is either known with some error from the beginning or changes over time [18]. The three main types of wildland fire spread models are stochastic, phenomenological, and physical [15]. There are different types of models for fire spread, each with its own benefits and limitations [19-21]. Equations governing combustion, fluid dynamics, and heat transfer are solved in a physical model to determine the spatio-temporal distribution of wildland fires [22-25]. Physical Models can be divided into simple and detailed versions [15]. In comparison to stochastic or phenomenological models, physical models are more general and can be real-time [26]. As an example of a physics-based model, Forbes [27], UoS [28], FIRETEC [29], PIF97 [30] and WFDS [31] include fuel fundamentals and their combustion and energy transfer. Statistics of historical wildland fires and prescribed burns are used to develop stochastic fire spread models [15]. In stochastic models, wind speed, fuel type, and soil moisture are summarized by their respective functional forms [21]. Phenomenological fire spread models rely on experimental measurements rather than models built from first principles to develop functional forms [19]. Rothermel's model [32, 33] of spread is one of the most widely accepted models for phenomenological time scales. Simulating wildfire spread numerically requires extensive computations at various ignition locations, which would be too time-consuming. The

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4 computational time for one fire spread simulation would be 872,000 min (about 600 days) on a
5 single processor [34].
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8 Moreover, wildfire spread can be predicted using fire spread simulation by employing cellular
9 automata (CA) or agent-based modelling (ABM). A forest is a cellular space containing cells that
10 are capable of influencing neighbor cells and changing their state. A simulation of fire spread is
11 based on proliferating cells that ignite neighboring unburned cells [35]. As an example, Clarke et
12 al. [36] integrated fractal geometry into a CA model to simulate wildfire propagation. As a method
13 for representing spatial heterogeneity in a set of interacting automata, Dunn and Milne introduced
14 a methodology for encoding fire spread in interacting automata. A landscape with heterogeneity
15 was captured and a simulation of wildfire spread was performed on a landscape with irregularities
16 and non-uniformities [37]. Hu and Sun (2007) developed three ways to suppress fire: direct attack,
17 parallel attack, and indirect attack [38]. Muzy et al. [39] used the CA model to simulate fire spread.
18 They combined it with Rothermel's physical model of fire spread [40]. For fire behavior
19 simulation, CA or ABM is more appropriate, but not for behavior forecasting [41]. Space and time
20 should be able to coexist seamlessly and concurrently in spatiotemporal forecasting [41].
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26 Recently, wildland fire forecasting has been greatly improved by using machine learning
27 algorithms [42-45]. Machine learning models predict new inputs based on observed knowledge
28 [46]. Data is the primary source of machine learning, meaning new scenarios are predicted without
29 any previous knowledge of the system or other models. The total burned area of a fire can be
30 estimated by machine learning methods based on meteorological data found in several studies [47-
31 51]. There is no attempt to assess the time-resolved spatial evolution of wildland fire fronts with
32 any of these methods; however, they are capable of predicting the overall burned area. Wildland
33 fires are initially predicted using NN [15] which are capable of reducing false alarms [52].
34 Wildland fire can be effectively predicted by support vector machine(SVM) [53, 54]. As a
35 prediction model of wildland fire, data mining technology has also been used [43, 55-59].
36 McCormick [60] presented an approach to predict the final burned area of a wildfire using machine
37 learning. In the model, an artificial neural network (ANN) classifies the center pixel of a 3×3
38 neighborhood based on whether it is burned or not. Wang et al. [61] estimates forest fire danger
39 rating online using a multiclass logistic regression (LR) model and the results show that this
40 approach is more accurate than least square fitting regression and random forest (RF) prediction.
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47 A fire front's location must often be predicted in a wildland fire spread model [15]. Krizhevsky
48 recently promoted convolutional neural network (CNN) in the 2012 [62] which were first
49 developed by LeCun in 1989 [63]. According to CNNs, the data must have an ongoing meaningful
50 relationship with a grid-like pattern [64]. To estimate the spatial evolution of wildland fire fronts,
51 Hodge et al. [15] propose the deep convolution inverse graph network (DCIGN). Based on GIS
52 data and deep learning algorithms, David et al. (2018) [65] concluded that the fire tends to spread
53 more rigorously to areas around the initial patch of fire. Satellite Images and Reinforcement
54 Learning (RL) are used by Subramanian & Crowley (2017) [66] to simulate the fire's reaction to
55 neighborhood landscape and environmental factors. The only parameters that were used were
56 temperature, wind speed, and wind direction. The proposed strategy by Lauer et al (2017) [67]
57 involves incorporating spatial interactions into a dynamically optimized way to curb the fire.
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Decisions made by management could now incorporate the spatial factors interacting with and affecting the spread of wildfire. There is a kind of ANN called a RNN which contains feedback channels that allow information to persist in the network [18]. The memory in RNNs prevents them from forgetting their inputs, unlike feedforward NNs [68]. Therefore, they can be used to analyze time series in a dynamic way. RNNs were used to predict the burned areas of wildfires using time series data, which allowed the output to be used as the input of the learning process [69]. By using RNN with non-completely connected connections and input based on Rothermel's model, Kozik, Nezhevenko, and Feoktistov [70] analyze forest fire behavior. With the ability to reserve historical information using selective gate modules, the long short-term memory(LSTM) is an advanced type of RNN [71]. A LSTM model was implemented to predict the extent of forest wildfires in the study by Liang et al. [12] In order to predict the extent of wildland fires, it is required to study hybrid models of NN, which can account for enormous factors and complex computations.

In this study, we developed a novel hybrid deep learning model to predict wildfire spreading based on time series of real fire data and meteorological factors. We implemented a fully connected convolutional neural network long short term memory (FC-CNN-LSTM) model to predict the forest fire spread in the coming day and reduce prediction time by using an appropriate cost function.

2. Propose framework

To develop a wildfire spread model, we need to get a proper set of related variables. The optimal variables set plays a very significant role to predict wildfire spreading. A high level view of the FC-CNN-LSTM model and the data used to train it is shown in Figure 1. In FC-CNN-LSTM, each driver of forest fire spread is represented as image channel. With its previous training, FC-CNN-LSTM predicts a new image with one channel representing the probability each pixel will burn. Future burn map is then generated from the predicted image post-processed.

Figure 1. A high-level schematic of proposed model. The left set of images show the different channels used as inputs to the deep learning model.

2.1. Data preparation

Figure 2 displays the study area Laura, Queensland, located in the northeast of Australia at latitude 144.299821 and longitude -15.783033. Global Fire Emissions Database(GFED) reports that this area experienced the second longest fire in history until 2016 [72-74]. From September 13, 2015 until December 12, 2015, the fire burned 91 days. We used the Visible Infrared Imaging Radiometer Suite (VIIRS) dataset [75] for the mentioned date. This dataset includes points shape files which represent active fires at given dates and can be accessed daily. The dataset also contains the wind speed and direction data collected from the nearest weather station to Laura [76]. As wind influences the evolution of a wildland fire, wildland fire spread models must capture the effect of heterogeneous and time-dependent wind conditions [15]. Also an increase in wind speed made wildfires more severe [2]. Meteorological data used in this study include precipitation, soil moisture, and runoff. Daily data collected from Australian landscape water balance [77] between September 13, 2015 and December 12, 2015. The intensity and spread of a fire will be reduced by increasing each of these variables. Land cover and vegetation characteristics have a great deal of influence on how fire spreads. There are some plants that are very sensitive to fire. Some areas are also devoid of vegetation, in this areas fire cannot spread. To obtain this information, the normalized difference vegetation index (NDVI) and land cover data are used. The European space agency (ESA) created the 2015 land cover to create long-term, consistent data for climate modeling [78]. Land cover in the study area is divided into six classes. First class included: tree cover, broadleaved, evergreen, closed to open (>15%). Second class included: tree cover, broadleaved, deciduous, closed to open (>15%). Third class included: tree cover, broadleaved, deciduous, open (15- 40%). Fourth class included: mosaic tree and shrub (>50%) and herbaceous cover (<50%). Fifth class included: shrubland. Sixth class included: deciduous shrubland (89). NDVI information is collected using the terra moderate resolution imaging spectroradiometer (MODIS) sensor called MOD13Q1. The data are generated every 16 days as Level 3 products with a spatial resolution of 250 meters (m) [79]. Fire spread is influenced by the characteristics of the earth's surface, for example Tariq et al. (2020) [80] found that larger forests with longer burn periods were located in the remote areas of low road coverage, which were mostly located at higher elevations. In this study three kinds of data were used including: elevation, slope and aspect. We collected elevation data from shuttle radar topography mission (SRTM), which has a 30 meter resolution. Slope and aspect data were derived from elevation.

Figure 2. Location of the burned area in Laura, Queensland, located in the northeast of Australia

2.2. Preprocessing

Preprocessing consists of two stages. In the first stage, some sets of data are preprocessed independently (for example, land cover data), then in the second stage, the entire set is preprocessed.

2.2.1. First Stage

Daily fire data are detected by the sensor at a certain time, and when the sensor passes over this area the next day, any new fires are detected. However, these fire points move during the day and are not static. The sensors cannot yet provide a temporal resolution of less than a day, so a method must be used to determine what area will be burned in a day. This challenge was solved by using a fixed radius and the density of points per day. GFED reported the average rate per day of fire spread in this area. Equation 1 calculates the constant value of the radius by taking into account the time, which is 24 hours.

$$Radius = \overline{Rate} \times T \quad (1)$$

In equation 1 \overline{Rate} is average rate of fire spread and T is time. The radius obtained from Equation 1 is used to calculate the density of points.

Normally, land cover data is classified as categorical data, meaning that each class has its own number. Each of these numbers is not superior to the other and only represents a class of its own. By using one hot encoding, the superiority of the numbers assigned to each class is eliminated. Since there are six classes of land cover in the study area, a map of zero and one has been made for each class so that where the desired class exists, the value will be one and otherwise the value will be zero.

Due to the limited temporal resolution of the data sources available, NDVI isn't available for all 91 days of the fire, so interpolation is performed for days without NDVI. To solve this challenge, combining NDVI data over a period of 16 days time step has been used to calculate NDVI for the second day (when NDVI is not available), the first day's NDVI (previous available NDVI data) data has been used except pixels which have been burned in that day. For these pixels NDVI obtained is from next available NDVI data. This procedure continues for days without NDVI data.

To gather data on wind direction and speed, the two nearest weather stations to study area have been used. Wind directions and speeds are reported daily by these stations. By using the weighted average of the values reported by the two weather stations, wind direction and wind speed were determined for each pixel. The distance of each pixel is calculated from weather stations and the inverse distance is used to weigh the speed and direction values of the stations. Equation 2 shows the wind speed calculation for each pixel. The wind direction is calculated similarly.

$$Velocity_{ij} = \frac{d_{ij-s1} \times velocity_{s1} + d_{ij-s2} \times velocity_{s2}}{d_{ij-s1} + d_{ij-s2}} \quad (2)$$

In equation 2, $Velocity_{ij}$ is wind velocity in i,j pixel, d_{ij-s1} is inverse distance between i,j pixel and first station, $velocity_{s1}$ is wind velocity reported by first station, d_{ij-s2} is inverse distance between i,j pixel and second station and $velocity_{s2}$ is wind velocity reported by second station.

2.2.2. Second stage

At this stage, two preprocessing steps are applied to all data, and not just one in particular. The spatial resolution of this data is different because this data is derived from different sources, so all of this data is resampled to 150m. In the dataset, the values of the variables vary widely, which may lead to computational complexity and poor prediction [2]. In order to make sure that all variables have equal weights, normalization must be used to transform the variables. To quantify the variables, Min-Max scaling [81] is used to transform the original variable ranges into new ones using linear transformation. The Min-Max formula is shown in Equation 3.

$$Z = \frac{x_i - \min(x_i)}{\max(x_i) - \min(x_i)} \quad (3)$$

The output variable is Z , the variables are x_i , and min is the minimum and max is the maximum value.

2.3. Network Structure

Figure 3 shows the FC-CNN-LSTM architecture used in this study. According to figure 1, the input images were 250×376 pixels with 16 channels. Each output image contains 250×376 pixels with one channel representing the probability a pixel has been burnt. The FC-CNN-LSTM is composed of three parts: a time distributed CNN, a LSTM and a FC architecture. All layers in the network presented in this work used rectified linear unit (ReLU) as activation functions except the last FC layer which used sigmoid activation functions. ReLU retains a number of linear properties because it is almost linear [82]. Also, according to researchers [83, 84], deep neural networks can learn more quickly and more accurately using ReLU than other activation functions. In the output layer, sigmoid activation functions are appropriate for scaling the activations of fire probability mask, since the output represents a probabilistic estimation of when each pixel will be burned. An Adam [85] optimizer was used to train the model with a batch size of 2 samples. Weights were initialized based on a normal distribution with a mean of zero and a standard deviation of one. Biases were set to zero as an initial value. All layers learned at the same rate of 0.0004 throughout the training. In this study, the success key was using the cost function, which is based on the similarity of two images called the dice coefficient [86-88]. Equation 4 represents the dice coefficient D between two binary images.

$$D = \frac{2 \sum_i^N p_i \times g_i}{\sum_i^N p_i^2 + \sum_i^N g_i^2} \quad (4)$$

where the sums run over the N pixels of the predicted binary image $p_i \in P$ and the ground truth binary image $g_i \in G$. A higher value of D indicates a higher similarity between the two images, and at the same time in the network training process the value of the cost function should be reduced, so the function shown in Equation 5 will be used as a cost function in the training process.

$$\text{Cost Function} = 1 - D \quad (5)$$

To avoid the model being over fitted and due to a lack of training data, three different techniques have been applied in this research. We used dropout [89] in the first technique at a rate of 0.3, L2 regularization [90] with a value of 0.0001 in the second technique, and cross validation [91] with 5 folds in the third technique. In the original dataset, about 80% was used as training data and the remaining 20% as test and validation data. In each dataset, we keep the chronological order of the images, since we are working on a forecasting task. Additionally, data must be transformed into (samples, time steps, rows, columns, channels) before training. Following the splitting of the dataset into input and output arrays shown in Table 1, a sample equal to (t-time step) is obtained, which corresponds to the batch size for the training step. In practice, time step is the number of occurrences in each sample, and here we take 4 as the time step value. Therefore, given a series of five images, the model will predict the next (fifth) occurrence.

Table 1. Splitting of the dataset into input and output arrays

Input	Output
[X ₁ , X ₂ , X ₃ , X ₄]	[Y ₅]
[X ₂ , X ₃ , X ₄ , X ₅]	[Y ₆]
[X ₃ , X ₄ , X ₅ , X ₆]	[Y ₇]
....	...
[X _{t-4} , X _{t-3} , X _{t-2} , X _{t-1}]	[Y _t]

Based on Google Colab graphics processing unit (GPU), the proposed network is trained in 200 epochs in 1 hour and 40 minutes.

2.3.1. Convolutional neural network framework

An effective network to extract features from complex datasets is CNN [62]. Equation 6 defines a typical convolution layer that contains the input image I and kernel K :

$$S_{ij} = \sum_m \sum_n I(m, n)K(i - m, j - n) \quad (6)$$

Where m and n are size of the kernel K .

2.3.2. LSTM framework

LSTM can capture long term temporal dependencies effectively [92, 93]. LSTM architecture consists of two components: a memory cell that can maintain its state over time and gating units that regulate information flow. There are three gates in the element cell structure: input, output, and forget. Formally, given a time series (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_t) with $x_t \in R^m$, a LSTM unit updates as follows.

$$f_t = \sigma(W_f[h_{t-1}; x_t] + b_f) \quad (7)$$

$$i_t = \sigma(W_i[h_{t-1}; x_t] + b_i) \quad (8)$$

$$O_t = \sigma(W_o[h_{t-1}; x_t] + b_o) \quad (9)$$

$$\tilde{C}_t = (W_C[h_{t-1}; x_t] + b_C) \quad (10)$$

$$C_t = C_{t-1} * f_t + \tilde{C}_t * i_t \quad (11)$$

$$h_t = \tanh(C_t) * O_t \quad (12)$$

i_t , O_t , and f_t are input gate, output gate and forget gate respectively, h_t is the hidden state at time t with size q over the entire hidden state. $W_f, W_i, W_o, W_C \in R^{m+q}$ are the weight matrices. $b_f, b_i, b_o, b_C \in R^q$ are biases. σ represents sigmoid function and $*$ is element-wise multiplication operator.

Figure 3. FC-CNN-LSTM architecture

2.4. Performance metrics

To evaluate the model's performance comprehensively, this paper uses precision, recall, F1 score, accuracy and balanced accuracy [94, 95] as the model evaluation indexes. Formulas (13) to (17)

correspond to the five indices used in the calculation. Figure 4 represents Confusion matrix which counts true labels and predictions.

		True Class	
		Positive	Negative
Predicted Class	Positive	TP	FP
	Negative	FN	TN

Figure 4. Confusion matrix which counts true labels and predictions

$$Precision(\%) = \left(\frac{TP}{TP + FP} \right) \times 100\% \quad (13)$$

$$Recall(\%) = \left(\frac{TP}{TP + FN} \right) \times 100\% \quad (14)$$

$$F1(\%) = \left(2 \times \frac{Precision \times Recall}{Precision + Recall} \right) \times 100\% \quad (15)$$

$$Accuracy(\%) = \left(\frac{TP + TN}{TP + FP + FN + TN} \right) \times 100\% \quad (16)$$

$$Balanced Accuracy(\%) = \left(\frac{\frac{TP}{TP + FN} + \frac{TN}{TN + FP}}{2} \right) \times 100\% \quad (17)$$

2.5. Post processing

FC-CNN-LSTM's output is a probability layer. To determine whether a pixel has been burned, a threshold value is applied based on the probability of fire. An experimentally determined threshold was used for post-processing. In this work, 0.77 was considered as threshold value. Fig 5 shows model's prediction before and after post-processing for a specific day on the fire.

(a) Before post processing

(b) After post processing

Figure 5. model's prediction before and after post-processing for a specific day on the fire

3. Results and discussion

The proposed model is estimated using all algorithms on the Google Colab platform using TensorFlow [96] backend. By considering 8 samples, the FC-CNN-LSTM model was examined for its ability to predict fire spread. The overall shape of the burn maps for the 4th day of the fire (one of the sample tests) predicted by the FC-CNN-LSTM is shown in Figure 6.

The analysis of variable correlations has been applied to the considering variables and the daily fire burned area in order to determine the effects of considered variables. According to Figure 7, there is a statistical relationship between the variables and the burned areas in everyday fires. The negative correlation value indicates there is an inverse relationship between this variable and fire burned area, indicating that one variable increases as the other decreases, and vice versa. When one variable increases or decrease in conjunction with another variable, there is a positive

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4 correlation. According to figure 7, there is an inverse relationship between meteorological
5 variables and fire activity on most days of the fire. In this case, the amount of precipitation is
6 negatively correlated with the burned area. Elevation has a positive effect on the spread of fire on
7 most days, and the intensity of the effect has increased on some days. There was a positive
8 relationship between the class 6 of land cover (deciduous shrubland) and the fire spread most days.
9 In this area, fires are more likely to spread through this type of land cover.
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12 Land cover is one of the factors that can significantly influence a fire spread. In the fire area, there
13 are six types of land cover. Figure 8 shows the percentages of area burned from each land cover
14 type. The correlation findings are consistent with Figure 7, which indicates that deciduous
15 shrubland is the most burned land cover type.
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Figure 6. The overall shape of the burn maps for the 4th day of the fire (one of the sample tests) predicted by the FC-CNN-LSTM

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3.1. Model performance

We used test data to prove the feasibility of the proposed model, which were not involved in the training process. Figure 9 shows the cost function value for training data and validation data during network training in different epochs. Based on Figure 9, the cost function value for validation and training data has been substantially reduced and the network training process shows no signs of over-fitting. After 200 iterations, the loss function value fell gradually and the model approached convergence stably.

Figure 8. the percentages of area burned from each land cover type.

A confusion matrix can be used as a valid test criterion in classification problems. Figure 10 shows the confusion matrix after the model was evaluated using test data. It was found that the model had a high level of accuracy in predicting burned pixels.

Figure 9. the cost function value for training data and validation data during network training in different epochs

Figure 10. confusion matrix after the model was evaluated using test data.

3.2. Model Comparing

In this paper, the proposed deep learning model is compared with other architectures. In some studies, fully connected networks (FCN) have been used to solve problems of classification and regression and they are considered classic supervised learning algorithms. A recurrent neural network is a type of neural network that processes time series information efficiently by performing recursion along the evolution of its input data. We developed a second FC-CNN-LSTM (FC-CNN-LSTM 2) model only using fire history data as input, without any meteorological or land information. In order to evaluate the performance, FCN, NN, RNN, and both FC-CNN-LSTM models have been used.

Figure 11 shows the metrics indexes of Precision, Recall, F1 Score, Accuracy and balanced accuracy for these models. Fire spread prediction is a difficult task, so memory-based models perform better than NN and FCN. There is vanishing gradient in RNNs, which causes poor results as compared to networks with long memory such as LSTM combined method has close results but the proposed model has a bit better results because of meteorological data and land data.

Figure 11. The metrics indexes of Precision, Recall, F1 Score, Accuracy and balanced accuracy

4. Conclusion

This paper presents a novel deep learning approach to predict fire spread called FC-CNN-LSTM. To train the model, we used meteorological, topographic, and land product data. Due to lack of training data we used three techniques to prevent network overfitting during training. After model training, test data was used to evaluate the model. Our proposed model was compared to other deep learning models, the proposed model has higher accuracy rather than other models in predicting fire spread. Additionally, we developed a model using the same neural network architecture, but with only time series fire data instead of meteorological data. Although this model achieved lower accuracy than the proposed model, it achieved better results than other models. This result demonstrates that the deep learning architecture we proposed is reasonable.

This model has an advantage over other models are developed for fire spread in that it is trained based on actual fire data, whereas most existing models are based on mathematical models outputs as training data and then evaluated in a real scenario. The process of generating training data using mathematical models which is a time consuming process is omitted in this study. Another advantage of the proposed model is the use of a different cost function from other existing models, so that existing models use simple indices such as MSE and MAE as cost function Nevertheless, these indices usually do not yield highly accurate results. In this research, dice coefficient has been used as a cost function. Previously, this function was mostly used in image segmentation problems and had good results. This function was chosen because of its good performance in predicting the spatial spread of fire. This model has the disadvantage of having a large number of parameters, which increases the complexity. We suggest reducing the number of network parameters by using encoder-decoder architectures instead of the fully connected layer in future research. Additionally, determining the threshold on the probability output of the network should be done more precisely. To optimize the results, optimization algorithms may be used.

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Declaration of interests

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: